

A novel transoral laser microsurgery device with rotary voice-coil actuators

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INTRODUCTION

Transoral laser microsurgery (TLM) is the preferred option for the resection of T1 and T2 laryngeal cancers [1]. TLM allows unobstructed microscopic visualization of the surgical site and accurate incisions, which are critical given the location and delicate nature of the involved organ. It contributes to superior surgical quality and post-operative quality of life by enabling surgeons to minimize surgical margins and better preserve healthy tissues.

Over the years, significant research and development efforts have led to a large increase in laser ablation quality. Laser power modulation, reflective focusing optics, and the use of scanners can now provide fine and clean tissue ablations with minimal thermal damage to surrounding tissue. However, the overall TLM surgical setup has hardly progressed in over 45 years. It is still based on the use of a surgical microscope placed in direct-line-of-sight with the surgical area. Fixed in front of the microscope, a joystick-controlled beamsplitter deflection mirror is used to steer the high power laser beam. This enables the surgeon to steer the laser with one hand while looking through the microscope and using the other hand to control another surgical instrument (e.g., a forceps). Regrettably, with this arrangement the much-needed accuracy in laser positioning remains heavily dependant on the surgeon skills and training. Furthermore, the use of the mechanical joystick and microscope present poor ergonomics and cause discomfort.

The issues mentioned above have motivated a great number of related research projects in recent years. Many focused on motorizing the laser micromanipulator, proposing robotic devices for precise laser steering control. Giallo *et al.* [2] proposed a servo-actuated mechanism to drive a traditional laser micromanipulator. Subsequently, Mattos *et al.* developed a fast steering mirror-based solution [3]. Then, Deshpande *et al.* proposed actuating the beamsplitter mirror directly using linear voice-coil motors [4]. Finally, Acemoglu *et al.* presented a clinically feasible design to actuate the beamsplitter mirror directly using a spherical mechanism driven by DC motors and backlash-free gearboxes. However, this design suffered from an excessively high cost, which resulted in an obstacle for commercial deployment.

The present research aims at addressing these technology limitations by designing a high performance micromanipulator offering mechanical simplicity, robustness and contained dimensions. To this end, the laser steering mechanism was entirely redesigned based on custom-made

rotary voice coil actuators (RVCA).

The use of RVCA provides outstanding advantages in the context of laser micromanipulation if compared to conventional DC motors. Even though they provide a limited rotation range, RVCAs offer small volume, low inertia and are adequate for high precision actuation [5]. Their high dynamics made them the ideal option for use in modern computer hard disk drives and medical ultrasonic scanners [6]. In addition, their high reliability and precision have made RVCAs a preferred option for mirror steering in the aerospace industry [7]. In the context of this work, the remote center of motion provided by these actuators allow for an elegant direct-drive solution for laser manipulation.

This paper presents the requirements and the design of this novel laser micromanipulator based on custom RVCAs. In addition, preliminary experiments with the developed device are described, demonstrating its feasibility and the successful achievement of key design requirements.

MICROMANIPULATOR DESIGN

The design requirements for the laser micromanipulator device include: 400 mm working distance; $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ workspace; $100 \mu\text{m}$ accuracy; and $50 \mu\text{m}$ resolution; In addition, the device must be compact and seamlessly replace the current manual devices to ensure easy integration into the current clinical setup.

Given these stringent requirements, here we opted for a direct-drive mechanism as illustrated in 1. This design can provide high stiffness and zero backlash. The direct actuation of the beamsplitter mirror avoids laser focusing issues, enables large workspace, and makes the device compatible with commercial scanners, which provide fast laser scanning motions for enhanced ablation quality. In addition, this design maintains the standard visibility of the surgical area through the surgical microscope.

As seen in Fig. 1, The proposed design uses two rotary voice coil actuators. The first degree of freedom (*roll*) is implemented using a large deep-groove ball bearing that enables unobstructed transmission of the laser beam. A custom-made flat-type moving coil RVCA is directly coupled with the bearing's rotor. The second degree of freedom (*pitch*) is directly mounted on the output of the first RVCA. Its rotor revolves around small ball bearings and is moved by a curved, moving-magnet RVCA.

This design guarantees that the two axis are orthogonal and that the laser beam reaches the beamsplitter mirror at the device's remote centre of rotation. This allows for decoupled

Fig. 1: CAD model of the new laser micromanipulator (a) and details on the RVCA-based mechanisms used for roll (b) and pitch (c). The developed prototype is shown in (d).

control of pitch and roll. Furthermore, special attention was placed on balancing the moving parts, allowing them to passively return to the central position when the system is not powered.

Finally, to enable closed-loop of the device, each rotor is fitted with a passive non-magnetized PCB codewheel and miniature high resolution inductive quadrature encoders. These encoders provide 2^{22} quadrature events per revolution, leading to an on-target resolution of $0.6\mu\text{m}$ and $1.2\mu\text{m}$ for the roll axis and pitch axis respectively.

DESIGN REALIZATION & EXPERIMENTS

The design described above was manufactured and assembled as a first proof of concept prototype of the technology. The prototype also incorporated an embedded controller, making it a fully integrated computer-assisted laser microsurgery device, which was named *CALM*.

Preliminary experiments demonstrated the feasibility of the design and its appropriateness to the intended transoral laser microsurgery application. *CALM* integrated seamlessly with the surgical microscope, occupying a volume similar to that of traditional laser micromanipulators and not imposing any additional restriction to the use of other microsurgery instruments (such as laryngeal forceps).

The device also demonstrated high performance, achieving fast laser steering motion (400 mm/s) and high precision ($20\mu\text{m}$) within a $100 \times 100\text{ mm}^2$ workspace at a typical 400 mm operating distance. An example of the image created by scanning the laser beam along a 5 mm circular trajectory at 40 Hz is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Image produced by the overlay of 3 video frames captured with the microscope camera when scanning of a 5 mm circular trajectory at 40 Hz .

CONCLUSION & DISCUSSION

The proposed RVCA-based laser microsurgery device demonstrated significant improvements with respect to our previously developed mechanisms, including smaller size and reduced mechanical complexity. It has also shown large improvements in terms of laser steering speed, accuracy and laser focusing quality. However, the use of direct-drive mechanisms combined with the need for high-speed actuation leads to a new challenge: The torque density of the voice coil actuators have to be maximised.

Our ongoing efforts also include enhancements to the embedded control system and comprehensive assessment of the device precision and accuracy. In addition, we are designing a new user interface for device control.

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